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The Virtual Fields Method applied to sandwich structures to obtain flexural modulus by modal analysis

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Abstract: The mechanical characterisation of panels by non-destructive testing allows to reduce costs and obtain additional structural information. Nearly three decades ago, Grédiac & Paris developed a non-iterative method for calculating the elastic properties of thin anisotropic composite plates under bending, called the Virtual Fields Method (VFM), using modal analysis under free-edge conditions. Despite being a classic method, there is still potential exploration for VFM, such as its application in sandwich structures, since there is no reference to the method applied to this material architecture. This work verifies the functionality of VFM by measuring the flexural modulus by modal analysis of a sandwich structure, statistically comparing the value obtained with data reported in the literature. The VFM proved to be statistically accurate.

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1. Introduction

The evaluation of properties of materials and structures by non-destructive tests (NDTs) is common in research fields [1-3], since it potentially tends to reduce the costs associated with the number of specimens commonly required experimentally. Nearly three decades ago, Grédiac & Paris [4] developed a non-iterative method to calculate the elastic properties of thin anisotropic composite plates under bending, called the Virtual Fields Method (VFM). The method is based on modal analysis under free-edge conditions, obtaining the stiffness values (D_{ij}) as a solution of a system – see Eq. (1) – in which the equations are given through a set of relevant weighting functions (virtual fields – x^2 , y^2 and xy), associated with different natural modes of vibration (W) and their natural

frequencies (ω). The method allows characterising an anisotropic plate by finding a homogenised plate with the same dimensions and equivalent global elastic properties.

In Eq. (1), ρ is the equivalent density of the plate; h is the plate thickness; x and y represent the coordinates of each plate point in the plane; and K_{xx} , K_{yy} and K_{xy} are described by Eq. (2). Typically, three modes of vibration (and their natural frequencies) are needed to identify all elastic constants: (I) bending along the x -axis, (II) bending along the y -axis and (III) torsion. The stiffness values D_{ij} can be used to calculate the elastic parameters, i.e., the flexural moduli along directions 1 and 2 (x and y), according to Eqs. (3) and (4).

$$\begin{bmatrix} \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots \\ K_{xx}^{(i)} & 0 & K_{yy}^{(i)} & 0 & 2 K_{xy}^{(i)} & 0 \\ 0 & K_{yy}^{(i)} & K_{xx}^{(i)} & 0 & 0 & 2 K_{xy}^{(i)} \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 2 K_{xy}^{(i)} & K_{xx}^{(i)} & K_{yy}^{(i)} \\ \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots \\ K_{xx}^{(j)} & 0 & K_{yy}^{(j)} & 0 & 2 K_{xy}^{(j)} & 0 \\ 0 & K_{yy}^{(j)} & K_{xx}^{(j)} & 0 & 0 & 2 K_{xy}^{(j)} \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 2 K_{xy}^{(j)} & K_{xx}^{(j)} & K_{yy}^{(j)} \\ \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} D_{11} \\ D_{22} \\ D_{12} \\ \dots \\ D_{66} \\ D_{16} \\ D_{26} \end{Bmatrix} = \frac{-\rho h}{2} \begin{Bmatrix} \dots \\ \omega_i^2 \int_S W^{(i)} x^2 dS \\ \omega_i^2 \int_S W^{(i)} y^2 dS \\ \omega_i^2 \int_S W^{(i)} (xy) dS \\ \dots \\ \omega_j^2 \int_S W^{(j)} x^2 dS \\ \omega_j^2 \int_S W^{(j)} y^2 dS \\ \omega_j^2 \int_S W^{(j)} (xy) dS \\ \dots \end{Bmatrix} \tag{1}$$

$$K_{xx}^{(i)} = \int_S \left(\frac{\partial^2 W^{(i)}}{\partial x^2} \right) dS; \quad K_{yy}^{(i)} = \int_S \left(\frac{\partial^2 W^{(i)}}{\partial y^2} \right) dS; \quad K_{xy}^{(i)} = \int_S \left(\frac{\partial^2 W^{(i)}}{\partial x \partial y} \right) dS \tag{2}$$

$$\frac{h^3}{12} \begin{bmatrix} D_{11} & D_{12} & D_{16} \\ D_{12} & D_{22} & D_{26} \\ D_{16} & D_{26} & D_{66} \end{bmatrix}^{-1} = \begin{bmatrix} D_{11}^{fn} & D_{12}^{fn} & D_{16}^{fn} \\ D_{12}^{fn} & D_{22}^{fn} & D_{26}^{fn} \\ D_{16}^{fn} & D_{26}^{fn} & D_{66}^{fn} \end{bmatrix} \tag{3}$$

$$E_1 = \frac{1}{D_{11}^{fn}}; \quad E_2 = \frac{1}{D_{22}^{fn}} \tag{4}$$

Despite the proven functionality of the VFM, there is no reference to classical works [4] on NDTs applied to sandwich structures. The reason is that the method applies to thin plates, i.e., structures under pure bending behaviour. However, in [5], the RJS Method states that sandwich materials can behave like thin plates under certain dimensions, depending on the core rigidity. It has been shown that in a quasi-static test (three-point bending) a sandwich structure can behave like a thin plate if the specimens have the necessary dimensions, and the slope of the linear portion of the normalised stress-strain curve is equal to the flexural modulus under pure bending. As example, the ACM FR (fire-resistant Aluminium Composite Material) was tested, which consists of a sandwich structure composed of a core made of low-density polyethylene reinforced with particles of magnesium hydroxide and aluminium skins.

The present work aims to verify the functionality of the VFM by measuring the flexural modulus via modal analysis of the ACM FR, statistically comparing the value obtained by Eqs. (1)-(4) with data reported in [5], measured via a three-point bending test.

2. Methodology

The modal analysis is performed according to the setup shown in Fig. 1. A 270x360 mm² ACM FR plate is used, which is larger than the minimum required for pure bending behaviour (90x180 mm²) reported in [5]. The plate is suspended by nylon threads (free-edge condition), and a mesh of 45x45 mm² square elements is constructed, totalling 63 points, under which reflective stickers are glued. The excitation (a white noise with an amplitude of 10 Vpp) is performed by a suspended shaker (TIRA TV 51110-M) coupled to a force transducer (Brüel & Kjær TYPE 8230-001) at point $(x,y)=(45,45)$. A laser Doppler vibrometer (Polytec Sensor Head OFV – 503) is used to measure the vibration response. VibSoft [6] is the software used for data acquisition, which allows the export of FRFs for data processing and analysis. Signals are sampled for all points, at a frequency of 8.2 kHz and Hanning window, with a 1 Hz high-pass filter to eliminate rigid body frequencies. The software used for data processing and analysis is ME'ScopeVES [7], which identifies the vibration modes and their natural frequencies based on the FRFs obtained for each measurement point using the Doppler vibrometer and the VibSoft software.

Fig. 1. Modal analysis setup.

The modes of interest (bending along the x -axis, bending along the y -axis, and torsion) are smoothed and interpolated in MATLAB [8], using the Lowess Quadratic Method with a span of 25%, so that the original modes with 63 points are converted to modes with 1037 points. The greater number of points makes the calculation of the derivatives present in Eq. (2) more accurate. The solution of Eqs. (1)-(4) for the calculation of the flexural modulus is also implemented in MATLAB. The Finite Difference Method is used for the calculation of derivatives, the Trapezoid Rule for the calculation of integrals and the Least Squares Method for the solution of the system constituted by Eq. (2) associated with each of the three vibration modes.

Finally, the flexural modulus obtained through the VFM (non-destructive method) is compared with that obtained by the three-point bending test (destructive method) reported in [5]. The comparison is performed using a statistical hypothesis test (one-sample t-test) using the Minitab software [9].

3. Results and Discussions

Fig. 2 shows the smoothed and interpolated mode shapes, and their natural frequencies. Table 1 shows the result of the flexural modulus obtained by the VFM and the comparison with data reported in [5]. The P-Value of 0.000 (<0.050) indicates that the flexural modulus of 23.78 GPa, measured by the VFM, is statistically equal to the flexural modulus obtained via three-point bending test, which shows that the non-destructive method described in this work is suitable for sandwich structures when the plate dimensions and the core rigidity meet the parameters defined by the RJS Method [5].

Fig. 2. Smoothed and interpolated mode shapes.

Table 1. Comparison between the flexural modulus obtained via VFM and three-point bending test.

	Three-point bending*	Virtual Fields Method (VFM)
Flexural modulus (GPa)	23.95	23.78
Standard deviation	±0.76	-
Coefficient of variation	±3.16%	-
P-Value <small>one-sample t-test</small>		0.000

* Data reported in [5].

4. Conclusions

Despite being a classic method proposed three decades ago, there is still potential exploration for VFM applications. This work showed that the VFM accurately measures the flexural modulus of sandwich structures if specific geometric parameters are met. This is in line with a recent study [5] that shows how sandwich panels

behave like thin plates under specific conditions. VFM tends to be more efficient regarding the number of specimens needed, as only one is needed. However, it should be noted that non-destructive methods are not dispensable, since the VFM does not allow the calculation of plastic parameters (such as yield and flexural strength).

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

CRediT author statement

R.J. da Silva: Conceptualisation; Methodology; Investigation; Data curation; Formal Analysis; Visualisation; Writing – original draft. **F.B. Batista:** Resources (laboratory instrumentation); Supervision (MSc advisor). **T.H. Panzera:** Supervision (MSc co-advisor); Writing – review.

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